

Thesis BSc Physics & Astronomy

Wind Energy Ramp Events

On the meteorological events causing sudden changes in wind energy generation

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Discussing 860 hours of work in 17 minutes, wish me luck!

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Motivation

- ▶ The aim of this study is to investigate which meteorological events are responsible for sudden changes in wind energy generation, called *ramp events*, at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster.
- ▶ Can cause difficulties in load balancing.
- ▶ Ramp events can lead to significant losses and instability in the grid.
- ▶ Will become more important as the share of wind energy in the total energy mix increases.

- ▶ This presentation will only discuss the key findings of the project.

Ramp definition and wind turbines

- ▶ In this study, the threshold definition of a ramp event is used. Such a definition is characterised by ramp size and ramp duration.
- ▶ A 500 MW ramp in 15 minutes means that the ramp caused a change of 500 MW or more in 15 minutes or less.
- ▶ A ramp only occurs if the wind speed change happens outside of the constant part of the power curve.

Figure: Left: An abstract power curve with cubic non-linear part, a constant plateau and cut-in/out thresholds. Right: The load factor of the entire Belgian offshore cluster plotted against wind speed measured at Borssele Alpha (not at turbine height).

Meteorology

Figure: Spatial and temporal scales for meteorological features in the mid latitudes. The styling is adapted from [1].

- Mesoscale features are harder to model and forecast than synoptic scale features.

This work: Research questions

What is the relationship between ramp event duration, size and the associated meteorological cause?

1. How do power generation and meteorological variables differ between seasons and time of day, and how does this relate to ramp events? **In thesis, not in slides.**
2. How important are low level jets for power production at the Belgian offshore cluster and do they cause ramp events? Can low level jet activity be noticed in production data without wind measurements at turbine height? **In thesis, not in slides.**
3. What meteorological features are responsible for ramp events at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster and in what quantities do these meteorological features occur? How can synoptic scale and mesoscale meteorological features be distinguished from each other in the power generation time series using meteorological data? → **Classification using dashboard**
4. How does the occurrence and size of ramp events depend on wind farm cluster size? → **Hypothetical clusters**
 - ▶ Hypothetical clusters are constructed by taking subsets of the real cluster.
 - ▶ Generation data from 10 individual farms lets us construct $2^{10} - 1$ subsets (*Powerset* $\mathcal{P}(S) - \emptyset$).
 - ▶ Allows us to see how many ramps would occur if the cluster would be smaller, and how different ramp statistics change as a cluster size increases.

This work: Classification - Associating ramp events with meteorological causes

Synoptic meteorological features that are known to cause ramping:

- ▶ **Low core passage**: Production change is mainly due to an **L-core** being in close vicinity of the cluster.
- ▶ **Low core cut-out**: Production change is due to an **L-core** near the cluster, causing a partial or total cut-out event.
- ▶ **Frontal related**: Production change is mainly caused by the passage of a front. This can be cold, warm, occluded or stationary fronts. This will include prefrontal lulls (reduction of wind speed before a front), the actual passage of a front and post-frontal relaxations.
- ▶ **Frontal cut-out**: Production change is a cut-out event incurred by wind speed changes due to a frontal passage.
- ▶ **Complex (synoptic)**: Ramp events where too many effects are at play to determine what the main driver was.

Figure: Different types of weather fronts.

This work: Classification - Associating ramp events with meteorological causes

Figure: Symbols for (a) a stationary front, (b) a trough aloft, (c) a (thunder)storm zone and (d) a convergence line.

Mesoscale meteorological features that are known to cause ramping:

- ▶ **Pre/Post-frontal convection**: Frontal related effects did occur, some time (<6 hours) before or after the ramp. May include troughs aloft, thunderstorm zones and convergence lines. **Heavily related to synoptic scale features, and it thus treated as synoptic scale.**
- ▶ **Non-frontal convection** (Mesoscale): No frontal related effects were likely to occur. Includes effects from rogue troughs aloft, organised thunderstorm groups and convergence zones.
- ▶ **Unknown** (Mesoscale): Cannot be explained with synoptic weather maps or with surface meteorological data from stations around the wind farm cluster.

Data: Wind farms and weather stations

Figure: Locations of wind farms and weather stations. Base layer: Google Maps

- ▶ Generation data
 - ▶ Elia for entire wind farm cluster
 - ▶ ENTSO-E for individual farms

- ▶ Meteorological data
 - ▶ KNMI Data Platform
 - ▶ KNMI Synoptic weather charts
 - ▶ Meetnet Vlaamse Banken

- ▶ None of these organisations are affiliated to this project.

Data: Data acquisition

The data acquisition for this project consisted of:

- ▶ Searching for relevant stations
- ▶ Using APIs for downloading data
- ▶ Reformatting/preprocessing
- ▶ ENTSO-E generation data - Web scraper

Actual Generation per Generation Unit
Actual Generation Output per Generation Unit (19/11/21)

Day and Time Range: 19/11/2021 UTC

Type	Generation Unit	Generation (MW)	Consumption (MW)	Detail
Wind Offshore	Nordseeoffshore-Windpark	22 (MW)		
Wind Offshore	Rosend Offshore-WP	24 (MW)		
Wind Offshore	Norther Offshore-WP	28 (MW)		
Wind Offshore	Nordseeoffshore 2	15 (MW)		

MWU	Generation	Consumption
00:00 - 01:00	26	
01:00 - 02:00	33	
02:00 - 03:00	23	
03:00 - 04:00	26	
04:00 - 05:00	22	
05:00 - 06:00	21	
06:00 - 07:00	13	
07:00 - 08:00	25	
08:00 - 09:00	26	
09:00 - 10:00	22	
10:00 - 11:00	32	
11:00 - 12:00	32	
12:00 - 13:00	26	
13:00 - 14:00	23	
14:00 - 15:00	25	
15:00 - 16:00	26	
16:00 - 17:00	9	
17:00 - 18:00	9	
18:00 - 19:00	13	
19:00 - 20:00	11	
20:00 - 21:00	38	
21:00 - 22:00	36	
22:00 - 23:00	36	
23:00 - 00:00	26	

▶ Screen capture of scraping process

Data: Ramp extraction and grouping

Figure: Ramp extraction method and grouping of ramp types.

Generation time series

- ▶ Decremental bids
- ▶ Ramp extraction
- ▶ `RXYYYZZ` is the code for a ramp type.
 1. `X` is `U` (up) or `D` (down).
 2. `YYYY` is the ramp size threshold in MW.
 3. `ZZ` is the ramp duration threshold in minutes.
- ▶ Ramp type grouping:
 1. **(B)** Counting every interval that satisfies ramp definition as a separate ramp.
 2. **(C)** Counting sequences of ramps as one (no overlap within ramp types).
 3. **(D)** Constructing a separate ramp type for overlapping ramp types:
 - ▶ Slow large `Only R100060`
 - ▶ Fast large `R100060 and R50015`
 - ▶ Fast small `Only R50015`
- ▶ In this presentation: Grouping method **D!**

Data: Ramp occurrence

- ▶ Number of ramp events varies per year.
- ▶ Contrast between 2023 and 2024 is large.

Classification: Associating ramp events with meteorological causes

Figure: Dashboard of an L-core passage. As the feature travels away from the cluster, a ramp-up occurs.

Classification: Associating ramp events with meteorological causes

PyQt6 application for classifying all ramp events.

DateTime: 2023-03-31 21:00:00
 Rtype: RD050015
 U/D: D
 Size: 500
 Dt: 15

EventID	Rt	dur	Mtype	I & Upsc	I & Upsc	asured &
197	2023-03-30 11:45:00 RU000000 U 1000 60 2023-03-30 11:45:00	0 days 00:15:00	Unknown (meso)	1658.46	2189.08	530.6199
198	2023-03-30 22:30:00 RU100000 U 1000 60 2023-03-30 22:30:00	0 days 01:00:00	Pre/Post-frontal convection (synop)	967.52	2115.55	1148.030
199	2023-03-31 20:15:00 RD100060 D 1000 60 2023-03-31 21:45:00	0 days 01:30:00	Low core passage (syn)	2159.31	837.61	-1321.69
200	2023-03-31 21:00:00 RD050015 D 500 15 2023-03-31 21:15:00	0 days 00:15:00	Low core passage (syn)	1604.81	1042.07	-562.74
201	2023-04-10 21:00:00 RU050015 U 500 15 2023-04-10 21:15:00	0 days 00:15:00	Pre/Post-frontal convection (synop)	1500.0	2001.59	501.5899
202	2023-04-12 10:30:00 RD050015 D 500 15 2023-04-12 10:45:00	0 days 00:15:00	Pre/Post-frontal convection (synop)	1537.36	725.37	-811.989
203	2023-04-12 10:45:00 RU100060 U 1000 60 2023-04-12 12:00:00	0 days 01:15:00	Pre/Post-frontal convection (synop)	725.37	1894.23	1168.86

The classification task distinguished between **R100060**, **R150060**, **R50015** and **R100015**. For these slides, the classification results have been regrouped to remove overlap (**Only R100060**, **R100060 and R50015**, **Only R50015**). Classification data set along with all dashboards are available in supplementary material.

Classification: Associating ramp events with meteorological causes

Assumptions

Some meteorological features have a recognisable fingerprint in weather data:

- ▶ Fronts often come with a clockwise wind direction shift and a temperature change. Cold fronts often have a pressure minimum.
- ▶ L-core passages often cause a large shift in wind direction (up to 180°).
- ▶ Thunderstorms often cause a temperature drop and a bumpy pressure evolution. This could be due to up- and downdraft regions.

- ▶ Large scale effects often cause homogeneous production changes across individual wind farms, whilst smaller scale effects often cause messy changes.

1. Classification: Occurrence of meteorological ramp drivers

Ramp driver	Only R100060			R100060 and R50015			Only R50015			TOTAL
	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total	
Counts										
L passage	5	5	10	8	3	11	1	0	1	22
L cut-out	0	0	0	2	1	3	0	1	1	4
Frontal related	20	16	36	16	15	31	7	12	19	86
Frontal cut-out	1	0	1	1	1	2	0	2	2	5
Complex (syn)	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Frontal convection	7	3	10	13	9	22	11	8	19	51
Non-frontal convection	2	3	5	4	7	11	6	7	13	29
Unknown (meso)	2	0	2	3	1	4	5	10	15	21
Total	39	28	67	47	37	84	30	40	70	221
Fractions										
L passage	0.023	0.023	0.045	0.036	0.014	0.05	0.005	0.0	0.005	0.10
L cut-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.009	0.005	0.014	0.0	0.005	0.005	0.018
Frontal related	0.09	0.072	0.163	0.072	0.068	0.14	0.032	0.054	0.086	0.389
Frontal cut-out	0.005	0.0	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.009	0.0	0.009	0.009	0.023
Complex (syn)	0.009	0.005	0.014	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.014
Frontal convection	0.032	0.014	0.045	0.059	0.041	0.1	0.05	0.036	0.086	0.231
Non-frontal convection	0.009	0.014	0.023	0.018	0.032	0.05	0.027	0.032	0.059	0.131
Unknown (meso)	0.009	0.0	0.009	0.014	0.005	0.018	0.023	0.045	0.068	0.095
Total	0.176	0.127	0.303	0.213	0.167	0.38	0.136	0.181	0.317	1.0

Table: Number of occurrences (upper table) and fractions (lower table) of each meteorological ramp driver for **Only R100060**, **R100060 and R50015** and **Only R50015**. Fractions sum to 1 over all events (221 total).

1. Classification: Seasonal and diurnal patterns of ramp events and their causes

Figure: Seasonal and diurnal patterns in ramp event occurrences and their causes.

- ▶ Majority is caused by frontal related effects.
- ▶ The second most common is (pre- or post-) frontal convection, commonly in the warm seasons.
- ▶ Cut-out events happen rarely in the warm seasons.
- ▶ Fronts can cause both up and down ramps.
- ▶ Non-frontal causes are more common in the warm seasons, but also have occurred often in autumn.
- ▶ The unknown events (possibly mesoscale) occur often in the warm seasons. All of the 21 unknown events occurred over only 14 days. This is important to keep in mind.
- ▶ Many ramp events occur in the late evening.

1. Classification: Relation between ramp size, ramp duration and their meteorological cause

Figure: Relation between ramp size, duration and meteorological cause. For every unique ramp event, their actual effect and duration (multiple of 15 minutes) has been averaged. The actual ramp events (coloured dots) have a slight vertical jitter added.

- ▶ Ramp-ups and ramp-downs have similar trends, both in terms of slope and ordering of meteorological causes.
- ▶ Mesoscale effects are more often associated with smaller ramps than with large ramps.

2. Hypothetical clusters: Relation between cluster size and ramp sensitivity

- ▶ For the smaller clusters, thresholds are scaled proportionally to installed capacity:

$$\frac{500}{2262} \approx 0.221, \quad \frac{1000}{2262} \approx 0.442$$

- ▶ For every possible subset ($2^{10} - 1 = 1023$) of the farms, all ramp events are extracted.
- ▶ Less ramp events occur for larger clusters (smoothing effect).
- ▶ Logarithmic versions with trend lines available in thesis.

Figure: Upper plot: Ramp occurrence against increasing cluster size.
 Lower plot: Fraction of total time the cluster is ramping.

2. Hypothetical clusters: Relation between cluster size and ramp sensitivity

- ▶ Absolute occurrence of slow ramps large stays roughly the same (blue, orange).
- ▶ Absolute occurrence of fast ramps decreases (green, red, purple, brown).
- ▶ Relative occurrence of slow large ramps increases (blue, orange).
- ▶ Relative occurrence of fast large ramps stays roughly constant (green, red).
- ▶ Relative occurrence of fast small ramps decreases (purple, brown).

Figure: Upper plot: Absolute occurrence (essentially the same plot as on the previous slide). Lower plot: Relative occurrence.

2. Hypothetical clusters: Relation between cluster size and ramp sensitivity

Figure: Average ramp duration. The shaded area corresponds to the standard deviation over observing time range.

- ▶ Large ramp events (especially fast large events) increase in duration for growing cluster size. This makes sense meteorologically, since features can be above the cluster for longer.

2. Hypothetical clusters: Relation between cluster size and ramp sensitivity

► Relative ramp size (in terms of load factor), does not change significantly as the cluster grows.

► Absolute ramp size increases as the cluster grows. Larger clusters have larger swings in production, as would be expected.

Figure: Upper plot: Relative average ramp size for each hypothetical cluster. Lower plot: Absolute average ramp size.

2. Hypothetical clusters: Relation between cluster size and ramp sensitivity

Figure: Product of ramp occurrence and absolute (average) ramp size. Could be used as a measure for the severity of ramps on the electricity grid. This is not a real physical quantity.

- ▶ "Total ramp energy" accounts for cluster size and ramp occurrence. Ramp occurrence decreases (for fast ramps) as size cluster increases, but absolute ramp size increases. This measure says something about the cumulative effect of all ramps over the observing time range.
- ▶ "Severity" decreases for fast small ramps (purple, brown).
- ▶ "Severity" increases slightly for fast, large ramps (green, red).
- ▶ "Severity" increases the most for slow large ramps (blue, orange).

Implications

The classification results suggest that for the current (real) cluster:

- ▶ Mesoscale effects often cause fast small ramps.
- ▶ Synoptic scale effects often cause slow large ramps.
- ▶ What type of ramp a frontal passage causes, seems to depend heavily on how the isobars are deformed.
- ▶ The dominance of frontal related ramp drivers might suggest that the cluster is sufficiently large to get quite insensitive to mesoscale ramp drivers.

The hypothetical cluster approach suggests that:

- ▶ The current (real) cluster is quite insensitive to small ramps when compared to hypothetical smaller clusters, although the decrease in sensitivity slows down (possibly asymptotically). This could mean that the sensitivity will not decrease much further for these fast small ramp types.
- ▶ Ramp duration grows slightly, possibly because meteorological features can affect the larger area for longer.
- ▶ The number of slow, large ramps is unaffected by the cluster size. This means that the "severity" increases as the cluster grows.

In conclusion, larger clusters ramp less frequently, but when they do, the events are more severe (larger and longer).

Limitations and improvements

There are some limitations of the approaches used in this project:

- ▶ Not enough data to do proper statistics on, especially when splitting the data in seasons and time-of-day blocks.
- ▶ Classification is done manually, which can introduce bias.
- ▶ The classification depends heavily on the KNMI synoptic charts, but the quality of these charts has not been assessed.
- ▶ The number of ramps extracted using the Elia data set (entire cluster), differs from when summed up ENTSO-E (individual farms) data is used. This is unexpected since Elia is the data provider for ENTSO-E.
- ▶ No farm-to-farm interactions have been accounted for. Is the hypothetical cluster method valid when wake effects can occur?

The methods used in this project could be improved by:

- ▶ Adding SCADA data to get a sense of the meteorological situation at turbine height.
- ▶ Adding LiDAR, Radar and better lightning detection data to study mesoscale features.
- ▶ Adding reanalysis data to benchmark ERA5 for wind energy related research.
- ▶ Using data with a higher temporal resolution.

Contributions and suggestions for further research

Suggestions:

It would be interesting to:

- ▶ Investigate the unknown causes in further detail.
- ▶ Apply the methods discussed on other wind farms, larger clusters with differently arranged turbines.
- ▶ Automate the classification process and including less extreme ramps (with longer duration). I suspect that other meteorological features will dominate for slower ramp events.
- ▶ Making the classification dataset large enough to be used as a training set for a machine learning model for a ramp forecasting based on weather forecasts.

Contributions:

- ▶ Proposing a method of combining threshold-based ramps into non overlapping groups.
- ▶ Developing a dashboard to inspect the meteorological situation during ramp events.
- ▶ Constructing a quantitative dataset with meteorological ramp drivers.
- ▶ Introducing an approach for investigating the effect of cluster size on ramp statistics.
- ▶ Introducing a severity measure for quantifying the effect ramping has on the total power output.

Thank you!

Questions?

You can view the full thesis, along with supplementary material here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1wGr0LmNAOH10-nDdaAnD_d8P1UajwiGx?usp=sharing

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- [1] C. D. Ahrens, P. L. Jackson, and C. E. O. Jackson, *Meteorology Today: An Introduction to Weather, Climate, and the Environment*. Toronto, Canada: Nelson Education, 2012, p. 704, ISBN: 9780176500399.